

THE CONTENT STRUCTURE OF OATHS.

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Abstract: in the article, the substantive structure of field oaths, the opinions of scientists about field oaths, the president's oath, its structure, speaking genres, in the process of highly developed cultural communication, for example, scientific, administrative-legal, political-ideological, artistic, religious (novel, drama, scientific researches, etc.) it is stated that speech genres that arise in the processes are understood.

Key words: industry, oath, oath, reflection, speech, genre, drama, novel, process, artistic, cultural.

The orderly molding of text content based on a specific internal plan creates a compositional structure. The great philosopher Aristotle said that a whole is something that has a beginning, a middle, and an end [93,49], that is, an internal sequence of whole and part. The Russian scientist A.A. Kibrik emphasizes that the genre scheme should be accepted as a configuration of passage types, and says that only then the possibility of linguistic analysis of genres will arise [94,11]. The composition (content-expressive construction) of the speech genre is a form created so that the listener can correctly feel and understand the content of the sentence, based on the speaker's specific planning. In science, M. Bakhtin's classification is widely used as a popular classification. M. Bakhtin divided oral and written, monologic and dialogic, primary and secondary speech genres distinguishes [95]. In the theory of speech genres, the scientist says that primary speech genres are speech genres that occur directly during communication, and secondary speech genres are those that occur in the process of highly developed cultural communication, for example, scientific, administrative-legal, political-ideological, artistic, religious (novel, drama, scientific research) etc.) speech genres that occur in the processes are understood. A.G. Baranov classifies speech genres as

primary simple speech genres, primary complex speech genres, secondary simple speech genres, secondary complex speech genres. S. Gayda concludes that speech genres can be classified in two ways. For example, simple and complex genres. Regular genres feature only one act. For example, intimidation, denial, swearing, etc. But in the introductory part of conversations or letters, one act, that is, a greeting, and in the following places, various speech acts appear depending on the purpose. At the end, it is the general end of the act of farewell. Swearing is a universal typological phenomenon for all languages. According to its function, in order for an oath to rise to the level of a speech genre, first of all, that sentence must be expressed by the speaker through a special form of the speech genre of an oath, that is, a compositional structure. By introducing the form of oath into the sentence expressing the speech actions of the speaker, the covenant, promise, and persuasion, the speech genre of oath in the real sense is formed. It seems that the speech genre of swearing is formed by speech units such as covenant, promise, and persuasion. Field oaths are external oaths. Let's analyze some of them. Presidential oath Oath of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I solemnly swear to serve the people of Uzbekistan faithfully, to strictly observe the Constitution and laws of the Republic, to guarantee the rights and freedoms of citizens, and to conscientiously fulfill the duties assigned to the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. (I do solemnly swear to faithfully serve the people of Uzbekistan, to strictly comply with the Constitution and the laws of the Republic, to guarantee the rights and freedoms of its citizens, and to conscientiously perform the duties of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan)¹⁰⁰. The thematic content of this oath followed the established laws which consists of serving the people, in a solemn, pathetic style and has a tone. The compositional structure of this oath is as follows: Presidential oath. Oath of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I solemnly swear to serve to comply to guarantee to perform in good faith oath model: $S_w = (S_1 + S_2 + S_3 + S_4) + p_m$ The structure of the composition of this oath (S_w) can be divided into two: 1) why the oath is taken (S); 2) oath part (p_m). Some types of oaths also have a third part: the concluding part (F). From the oath model

shown in the table, it can be seen that the oath is directed from the bottom up, that is, first the reason for the oath is given, and then the part of the solemn oath is given. The uniqueness of the personal oath is that this oath is solemnly sworn by signing the Qur'an and the Constitution. Symbols (flag, coat of arms) will be displayed on the background.

Military oaths Military oaths include youth members of the Armed Forces of Uzbekistan and the oath of an officer of internal affairs. For example, a soldier's oath: Soldier's oath As I enter the ranks of the Armed Forces of Uzbekistan, I solemnly swear to be loyal to my people and my President. I take an oath to consider the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan as sacred, to obey them, to obey military regulations, the orders of commanders and chiefs, to strictly observe military discipline, to be an honest, brave and alert warrior. I swear in front of the spirit of our ancestors to remain a loyal son of my motherland until my last breath, to steadfastly overcome all hardships and difficulties of military service, to keep state and military secrets. I swear to be a defender of the country's interests and independence for the bright future of our dear Uzbekistan. If I break this oath, I will be subject to the punishment prescribed by the laws and the hatred of my people [101]. The military oath becomes a permanent oath, and after a certain preparation, the soldiers solemnly take an oath. The compositional structure of the soldier's oath is as follows: Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan at the Ministry of Internal Affairs Academy of Uzbekistan the oath of office staff I solemnly swear I swear I swear I swear. [101] be happy oath model: $Sw = pm_1 + pm_2 + pm_3 + pm_4 + F$ It seems that the oath is directed from the bottom to the top, and at the end of the oath there is a part that serves to strengthen the above oath (mubatalo bolai). "I swear" is being used repeatedly. Further repetitions were used as confirmation of the phrase "I solemnly swear" at the beginning of the oath.

Oath of lawyers We included the oaths of judges, prosecutors, and notaries in the oath of lawyers. Lawyers take an oath in front of the State flag of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and in the Republic of Karakalpakstan - in front of the State flag of the Republic of Karakalpakstan - in a solemn situation, and it is this sign that distinguishes the oath of lawyers from other

oaths. Jurists' oath is temporally permanent, locally different local, and quantitatively plural oaths. The oath of court officials is divided into two types: 1. Oath of the Judge of the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan. 2. Oath of judges. According to Article 70 of the Law on Courts, judges take the oath in the following order: judges of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan, judges of regions, Tashkent city courts, inter-district, district (city) courts and military courts, judges of economic courts O' at the session of the Plenum of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan; Judges of the supreme courts of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, inter-district, district (city) courts at the meeting of the presidium of the respective supreme courts of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. It seems that the local character of the oath of judges is reinforced by the Law on Courts [102]. Oath of the Judge of the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the analysis of the judges' oath is as follows: Judge of the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan oath I solemnly swear to fulfill the duties of a judge of the Constitutional Court honestly and conscientiously, to protect the Constitutional system, and to obey only the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Judge's Oath I solemnly swear to carry out the tasks entrusted to me honestly and conscientiously, to administer justice only in accordance with the law, to be impartial, impartial and fair as my duty and conscience dictates as a judge. Both oaths are judges' oaths. These oaths are thematically different, while the content of the Oath of the Judge of the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan is to obey and protect the Constitution, the oath of a judge is to perform judicial duties fairly while obeying the law. In terms of content, the first oath is more important and stronger. The compositional structure of both oaths is the same: Judge's Oath I solemnly swear to perform honestly and conscientiously to protect the constitutional system to protect the constitutional system in compliance with the law to increase to obey the constitution to be unbiased, impartial, fair oath model: $S_w = (S_1 + S_2 + S_3 + S_4 + S_5) + p_m$ [102] Law on Courts. Adopted by the Legislative Chamber of the Republic of Uzbekistan on June 15, 2021. Approved by the Senate on June 26, 2021. <http://lex.uz/docs/54458> 04/2/2022. Oath of medical staff The oath of medical

personnel includes the oath of doctors and students enrolled in medical schools. Doctors around the world take an oath called the Hippocratic Oath. Below, let's analyze the oath of doctors and college students. Oath of doctors of the Republic of Uzbekistan I, taking the high title of a doctor and entering the medical profession, devote all my knowledge and skills to the treatment of patients and the maintenance of human health; to provide medical care to every patient, regardless of age, sex, race, language, religion, belief, social origin, without sparing my energy and time; to put the patient's health above my personal interests, to be humble and honest, to constantly improve my knowledge and skills; to keep the doctor's secret; to give people confidence that they will always find mercy and healing; I solemnly swear to continue the glorious traditions of great doctors like Abu Ali Ibn Sina. I swear to be faithful to this oath until the end of my life. The compositional structure of the oath is as follows: The compositional structure of the oath of medical personnel to dedicate to help to keep I solemnly swear to continue oath model: $S_w = (S_1 + S_2 + S_3 + S_4) + p_m$ It seems that the model of the oath differs only from the military oath, it is structurally the same as the rest. Thematic content consists of treating patients and maintaining human health. One of the peculiarities in the text of the oath is the presentation of ideas of religious tolerance. The symbol of nationality is the mention of the name of our great grandfather Abu Ali ibn Sina. All of these are deictic signs of how important the text of the oath is. The oath is temporally permanent, locally different, and quantitatively plural. The text of this oath differs from other oaths in that it is formed in the first person plural and is combined with the oath of the participants of the sports competitions "Umid Nihollar". These texts are written with the meaning of patriotism (a child loyal to the motherland, supporting the country, raising the glory of the homeland) and achieving great achievements in sports. The oath "Universiada" [95] belongs to the type of temporally permanent, quantitatively plural, and locally different type of local oath. Oath of education staff Education workers, like employees of various fields, take an oath. Young teachers are sworn in at the traditional August councils of city and district teachers who are starting their careers. These oaths are

temporally permanent, locally different types of local, and quantitatively plural types of oaths. Below we will consider the oaths of students of higher education. Technical University named after Abu Rayhan Beruni student oath As I join the ranks of students of Tashkent State Technical University, I solemnly swear: to preserve the glory and dignity of the citizenship of the independent Republic of Uzbekistan; with all my work and intelligence to help its economy, science and culture flourish, to restore rich national traditions, and to help all peoples and peoples living in it to live in peace and harmony; to defend the independence and constitutional system of the republic with all my might, to strengthen the authority of the presidency and the reputation of the President elected by the people; to fight against any attempt to cast a shadow on the pure name of my hard-working and honest people, to do everything in my power to prevent the tears and suffering of innocent people; Taking into account the sad lessons of the bloody events in Karabakh, Moldova, Georgia and Tajikistan, to deal a decent blow to any subversive forces that seek to disrupt stability in the republic for their own selfish goals; to diligently and consistently acquire knowledge in my chosen specialty, to always and tirelessly improve my general and cultural level, [96] to enjoy the values of world science and culture; To deeply study and widely promote the invaluable heritage of Uzbek scientists who became the great figures of world science and culture such as Navoi, Ulugbek, Beruni, ibn Sina, al-Khorazmi and others; to be correct, humble, fair and conscientious, to show deep respect for my teachers and mentors, to respect their work and life experience and to use it effectively, to respect the elderly, to help the disabled and helpless, to protect the weak; to raise the reputation of our "Alma-Mater" - Tashkent State Technical University named after Abu Rayhan Beruni with all our activities and try to get it recognized by others; With my pure conscience, my free will, and a deep sense of civic responsibility, I solemnly say that I will always honor my oath and remain faithful to it for life. I solemnly swear the oath of the students of Technical University named after Abu Rayhan Beruni

... .. to keep sacred

... .. to strengthen

... .. to do the work

... .. to strike

... .. to promote

... .. to protect

... .. to act

I will remain faithful for a lifetime oath model: $S_w = (S_1 + S_2 + S_3 + S_4 + S_5 + S_6 + S_7) + pm + F$ Student's oath consists of seven S units, one pm predicate and F finish. As can be seen from the model of the oath, the text of the oath is quite complex made up. At the beginning of the text, a solemn oath is taken, and then the content of the oath is revealed. At the end of the text, there is a concluding section that reinforces the oath, which makes the text a whole and composes the composition. The text of this oath differs from the above-mentioned oath texts in its complexity. The thematic content is also widely covered.

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